

The Influence of Convenience, Benefits, Security and Trust on the Interest in Using Financial Technology in OVO Applications as a Digital Payment

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ABSTRACT: This study aims to obtain data and find out the influence of convenience, benefits, security and trust on the interest in using financial technology in OVO applications as a digital payment study in the case of accounting students at the Faculty of Economics, Prima Indonesia University. The data collection method in this study used a questionnaire. This sampling technique data collection is using accidental sampling and a total of 102 respondents at the Prima Indonesia University. The results obtained in this study show that convenience and benefits do not have a significant partial influence on the interest in using financial technology in OVO applications as a digital payment, whereas security and trust have a significant partial influence on the interest in using financial technology in OVO applications as a digital payment. Simultaneously, convenience, benefits, security and trust have a significant influence on the interest in using financial technology in OVO applications as a digital payment.

KEYWORDS: Convenience, Benefits, Security, Trust, Interest in use, Financial Technology, Digital Payment

I. INTRODUCTION

Information and communication technology has developed very quickly and rapidly and affects people in all aspects of life. The ease of technology that makes it easy for the community is something that cannot be separated from human life. Technological developments also affect the economic system, especially finance, which has begun to implement the digital economy or digital payments such as mobile banking, internet banking, and fintech. One of the most popular financial technology payments in Indonesia is Join The Revolution In Payment or better known as OVO. The existence of financial technology in the financial system is slowly starting to change habits and payment systems in people's lives.

The convenience and benefits offered by digital payments or electronic money can affect the increase in users in the digital payment applications offered. A product service will be in demand and used by the wider community if the product service has benefits and convenience in helping payments in daily life. The company's ability to protect consumers' identities that are registered in the applications when using digital payment facilities from fraud and data theft is a very important thing. The more secure a system is, the more confident consumers will be to use it and attract the interest of the consumer. Perceptions of the level of trust in the products used can also affect the interest in using electronic money as digital payments. Public trust is one of the keys to ensuring and maintaining the relationship between customers and service providers.

There is a case phenomenon which states that the OVO server is experiencing problems such as the OVO balance cannot be used so that the transaction fails suddenly and the use of other people's personal data but passes the OVO verification stage makes the owner suffer losses. This case reduces consumer confidence in using OVO application and the benefits and interest felt by users from the existence of the service is also decreasing so that it will affect the interest in using the service again (detik.com and mediakonsumen.com). Therefore, related to this phenomenon, it becomes something interesting to study.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Convenience

Perception of User Ease is a benchmark for someone who believes that the technology can be easy to use. The level of convenience felt by a person when using and operating a technology in this case OVO will affect the level of that person's desire to use OVO in the future or at the time of the next transaction (Yusda, 2020). The higher the ease of a person in the use of

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technology used then the higher the benefits obtained if the system is easy to understand and practical then consumer interest in the use of OVO applications will also increase (Latief, 2020).

Benefits

The perception of benefits is a benchmark for how the use of technology can generate benefits for its users, meaning that the more someone believes in the usefulness of a service with the performance of the system, the interest in its use will also increase (Yusda, 2020). The higher the benefits provided by digital payments with OVO Fintech, the more consumer interest in using it will increase (Atriani, 2020).

Security

Perception of security is a belief in the use of a secure system that is free from the risk of loss or loss of data as well as a low risk of theft related to users' personal information which is guaranteed to be confidential and free from third party interference (Iliyini, 2020). The more an application or digital payment can provide security guarantees against online crime both with an enhanced security system, it will form public trust in using electronic money so that consumer interest in using it will increase (Jelita, 2020).

Trust

Trust is the main thing in determining the success of a product or service because it is the reason consumers use a product in the long term and is part of the relationship between consumers and marketers (Purba, 2020). Trust will affect a person's intention to use OVO repeatedly for the convenience of their transactions, where the level of trust in the perceived ease of transactions will affect the intensity of using OVO technology as a digital payment (Yusda, 2020).

Conceptual Framework

III. METHOD

Population is the total number of units or individuals whose characteristics are to be studied. In this study, the population of this study is the accounting students at the Faculty of Economic, Prima Indonesia University with a total of 102 people. Therefore, using all populations without having to attract sample as a unit of observation is called accidental sampling. In this study, it was designed with quantitative research. Quantitative research is research that has a tendency to be analyzed by means or statistical techniques. The data can be in the form of numbers or scores and is usually obtained using a data collection tool whose answers are in the form of a range of scores or weighted questions (Sugiyono, 2017). The data collection technique used a questionnaire with the help of a google form which was distributed to the accounting students of the Faculty of Economics, Prima Indonesia

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University, who were willing to fill out the questionnaire. Data analysis technology is using SPSS or Statistical Package for Social Science.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity and Reliability Test

The validity measurement result using Pearson Correlation shows that all indicators have Pearson Correlation value above $r_{table} = 0,1927$. Cronbach's Alpha is a reliability that measures the lowest value (the lower limit) of the reliability of a variable. Priyatno (2017) states that a latent variable has a high reliability if the reliability of cronbach's alpha above 0,6.

Table 1. Validity and Reliability Test

	PEARSON CORRELATION		CRONBACH'S ALPHA
	Indicator	Value	
CONVENIENCE	X1	0,754	0,723
	X2	0,796	
	X3	0,758	
	X4	0,795	
BENEFITS	X5	0,869	0,894
	X6	0,859	
	X7	0,891	
	X8	0,874	
SECURITY	X9	0,917	0,881
	X10	0,892	
	X11	0,797	
	X12	0,826	
TRUST	X13	0,863	0,843
	X14	0,896	
	X15	0,889	
	X16	0,873	

Multiple Regression Analysis

Viewed by the results of the data statistical analysis with the help of SPSS the following multiple linear regression results are obtained:

Table 2. Regression Result Coefficients*

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2,190	1,504		1,456	,149
Convenience (X1)	,143	,077	,165	1,849	,068
Benefits (X2)	,121	,088	,121	1,376	,172
Security (X3)	,345	,084	,351	4,108	,000
Trust (X4)	,270	,094	,272	2,864	,005

a. Dependent Variable: Interest_In_Use(Y)

Based on table 2, it can be arranged a research model with the following regression equation:

$$Y = 2,190 + 0,143X1 + 0,121X2 + 0,345X3 + 0,270X4$$

The multiple regression equation model means:

1. The constant value is 2,190 which means that if the independent variables, namely convenience (X1), benefits (X2), security (X3) and Trust (X4) are equal to zero, then the interest in use (Y) is 2,190.
2. The value of the regression coefficient X1 = 0,143 indicates that every increase in convenience, the interest in use is increased by 0,143. This can be seen from the value of the standardized coefficients in table 2.

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- The value of the regression coefficient $X_2 = 0,121$ indicates that every increase in benefits, the interest in use is increased by 0,121. This can be seen from the value of the standardized coefficients in table 2.
- The value of the regression coefficient $X_3 = 0,345$ indicates that every increase in security, the interest in use is increased by 0,345. This can be seen from the value of the standardized coefficients in table 2.
- The value of the regression coefficient $X_4 = 0,270$ indicates that every increase in trust, the interest in use is increased by 0,270. This can be seen from the value of the standardized coefficients in table 2.

Coefficient of Determination Value

Explaining the ability of the variation model that is related to the dependent variable is the purpose of the Coefficient of Determination. The following is a table of the Coefficient of Determination.

Table 3. Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,723 ^a	,523	,503	1,601

a. Predictors: (Constant), Convenience, Benefits, Security, Trust

b. Dependent Variable: Interest_in_Use

Based on the table above, the resulting Adjusted Square value is 0,503. It can be interpreted that the dependent variable of 50,3% is influenced by the independent variable and the other 49,7% is influenced by variables that are not examined.

F-Test Result

Table 4. Simultaneous test (F)

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	272,367	4	68,092	26,578	,000 ^b
Residual	248,506	97	2,562		
Total	520,873	101			

a. Dependent Variable: Interest_In_Use

b. Predictors: (Constant), Convenience, Benefits, Security, Trust

The purpose of conducting the simultaneously test is to evaluate whether the independent variable together have a significant effect or not on the dependent variables. Based on the table 3, it can be seen that there is a significance of 0.000 which is smaller than 0.05. This shows that the convenience, benefits, security and trust together have a positive and significant effect on the interest in using financial technology in OVO Application as a digital payment which explains that hypothesis is accepted because the $F_{value} > F_{table}$ ($26,578 > 2,47$) and a significant value of $0,000 > 0,05$.

t-Test Hypotheses

Table 5. Partial Test (t)

Model	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)	1,456	,149
Convenience (X1)	1,849	,068
Benefits (X2)	1,376	,172
Security (X3)	4,108	,000
Trust (X4)	2,864	,005

a. Dependent Variable: Interest_In_Use(Y)

The significant value of the convenience (X1) variable is $0,068 > 0,05$, which means that H1 is unacceptable. Based on the table above, it is found that the calculated t value is 1,849. Then it is found that $1,849 < 1,985$. Then it means that convenience (X1) has no effect and is not significant on the interest in use (Y) variable. The significant value of the benefits (X2) variable is

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0,172 > 0,05, which means that H2 is unacceptable. Based on the table above, it is found that the calculated t value is 1,376. Then it is found that 1,376 < 1,985. Then it means that benefits (X2) has no effect and is not significant on the interest in use (Y) variable. The significant value of the security (X3) variable is 0,000 < 0,05, which means that H3 is acceptable. Based on the table above, it is found that the calculated t value is 4,108. Then it is found that 4,108 > 1,985. Then it means that security (X3) has a significant effect on the interest in use (Y) variable. The significant value of the trust (X4) variable is 0,000 < 0,05, which means that H4 is acceptable. Based on the table above, it is found that the calculated t value is 2,864. Then it is found that 2,864 > 1,985. Then it means that trust (X4) has a significant effect on the interest in use (Y) variable.

DISCUSSION

Convenience does not have a significant and positive influence on the interest in using OVO applications as a digital payment. Technology continues to develop rapidly so that people, especially students, have become accustomed to the use of new technology so that convenience is no longer a benchmark in determining the use of applications, especially for the millennial generation who like to try new things in an application (Ernawati, 2020).

Benefits do not have a significant and positive influence on the interest in using OVO applications as a digital payment. Users will ignore the benefits because of the security reason that becomes the important factor in user decisions so that it does not have a major impact on influencing the interest in using an application (Ernawati, 2020).

Security has a significant and positive influence on the interest in using OVO applications as a digital payment. Security in providing information and protection in electronic money when making transactions is an important factor and will increase interest in using an electronic money application such as the OVO application so that users feel safe in using electronic money (Yanto, 2020).

Trust has a significant and positive influence on the interest in using OVO applications as a digital payment. The more trusted an application or electronic money service, the user will feel safe and calm in using the application because it has a responsibility, service system and especially high integrity towards data security and user electronic money (Pratama, 2019).

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of research and discussions conducted by researchers regarding the influence of convenience, benefits, security and trust on the interest in using financial technology in OVO Applications as a digital payment, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Convenience does not have a significant and positive influence on the interest in using financial technology in OVO applications as a digital payment.
2. Benefits do not have a significant and positive influence on the interest in using financial technology in OVO applications as a digital payment.
3. Security has a significant and positive influence on the interest in using financial technology in OVO applications as a digital payment.
4. Trust has a significant and positive influence on the interest in using financial technology in OVO applications as a digital payment.
5. Convenience, Benefits, Security and trust have a significant and positive influence on the interest in using financial technology in OVO applications as a digital payment.

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